

Mukimi's poem "Clay(Loy)" reflects today's current problems

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ABSTRACT

In this article, there are opinions about the meaning of some verses in Mukimi's poem "Loy" that emphasize today's problems. Information about the problems of road construction at the international and Uzbek level today and their innovative solutions. data and conclusions are given.

In the history of our national literature, the literary heritage of the authors who grew up in the Kokan literary environment of the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century has a special place. The works of Muhammad Aminkhoja Muqimi, a prominent representative of this literary environment, have always been the focus of experts' attention. Many studies have been done on the poet's works. Unfortunately, Muqimi's works were interpreted one-sidedly in accordance with the ideology of the Shura era. As a result, the poetic heritage of the poet was removed from its main essence. That is, his works were edited, shortened, remained in the sources. This, in turn, puts on the agenda the necessity of impartial and truthful study of the poet's literary heritage based on new criteria.

Muqimi started the "Travel" genre in Uzbek literature during the period of national renaissance. It harshly criticizes the conflicts of the time, the tsarist government's burdens on the people, oppressive and unjust ruling groups, and describes the ruined and destroyed villages. Mukimi carefully observes the real reality and people's life, describes the life of ordinary people with love and pity, on the other hand, he exposes the tsarist officials and their local officials with hatred and anger. The poet uses his comic talent and mercilessly exposes the true characters of the hypocrite thousands, unjust judges, dishonest rich people and others. Mukimi sang real love, human being. The essence of his poems are human experiences, joys and sorrows, desires and dreams, struggles. In them, friendship, loyalty, sincerity, loyalty, endurance and fortitude were glorified, and through these, the poet tried to educate people's good qualities. He dreamed of a fair and happy time, he believed that such days would come ("A time is as good as if you don't live in the end" and others). Hope for the future and dreams and ideals of a prosperous life are reflected in his poems, which contain situations of longing, complaints, and dissatisfaction.

The conflict between the critical worldview and aspirations and the environment brought out a critical direction in his work. This is more reflected in his behavior. The humor is divided into satire and humor. In his satires, the exploits of Tsarist officials and some local rich people were exposed ("Tanobchilar", "Toy", "In the description of a Muscovite rich", "Hajvi Victor rich", "Voqelai Victor" and others) - "Election (Literature)", "Dar mazammati zamona" " and others show the capitalist and immoral relations entering the country and their consequences. Sometimes, following the prevailing views of the time, Dukchi also wrote satirical works about Eshan ("Hajvi halifai Mingtepa").

He created about 30 comic works on topics such as horses, carts, mud, flies, and malaria. In them, the poet laughed at the backward and ugly aspects of life, defects in the social consciousness, the pain of colonialism, the desolation with venom ("Devonamen", "Ko'samen", "Hayron keridi loy", "Pash-shalar", "Shikoyati bezak" and others). A number of other comics reflect a new attitude to changes in the life of the society ("Definition of the oven", "Build a cart", "Mud", etc.).

MUD

But he was surprised to go out,
It snowed, spring returned, winter made mud.
As the snow continued to fall on the storm
He regretted it until he died.
In winters without rain and snow, spring is the season,
The uprooted carrot was hidden in the clay.
This poor, not rich, suddenly stepped on his feet,
When I hit the ground, the wrestler made mud.
He went to the street and stole Muqimi's head.
He did good, his soul turned a disbeliever into a Muslim.

The poet skillfully describes the content of the passage below in the first verses. It is said that when the poet was getting ready to go out, it was snowing, and when he said that spring has come, it rained and winter was around. It is not an exaggeration to think that the word "Zimiston" in Misra is the reason why Muqimi's heart was darkened: that is, the roads are muddy and there is no way to walk.

If we look at the cross-section of issues, today the most initiatives in the issue of road repair are the projects that are being postponed... And in the cross-section of regions, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Khorezm and Andijan are leading in terms of the number of projects related to road defects." Even in the first seasons of the "Initiative Budget" project, the direction of road repair was always in the first place. For this reason, a separate system called "My Way" was created on a smaller scale, similar to "Initiative Budget". Because of these problems, it is announced that road construction is considered one of the most painful and problematic areas not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world media. Especially today, under the influence of anomalous weather, the roads look like they were after the war.

In the years of independence, the leadership of the Republic adopted a number of programs aimed at the development of communication and road transport infrastructure. Decision No. PQ-2313 "on the program" also serves to develop the road transport

infrastructure in our country. Construction and reconstruction of about 513 kilometers of highways were carried out in connection with the modernization of the Uzbek national highway, for which 1379.4 bln. it was decided to allocate investment funds in the amount of soums . In the near future, a huge national highway will be put into operation, which will further increase the economic potential of New Uzbekistan. As a result, the following positive changes are expected in the road transport system:

- 60-70% increase in cargo and passenger transportation of automobile transport within the republic;
- increase of international and transit car transport by 45-55% on average;
- establishment of developed road infrastructure;
- reducing accidents and the negative impact of the republic's road transport system on the environment;
- completion of the next stage of formation of a single, integrated and efficient network of motor transport communications of the country. These positive changes have a direct impact on the mood of the population. As mentioned in the above poem, it is mentioned in the last stanzas that the bad roads also affected the great poet who lived with the pain of the people. Let's realize that it is a sad situation that the problems of the 20th century have reached today, and let's eliminate this problem and contribute so that the future generations will not suffer from this problem.

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